

Chapter 3

Effects from the Implementation of Third European Road Safety Action Program using Synthetic Control Methods and Interactive Effects Counterfactual Approaches

3.1 Abstract

The effect of the Third European Road Safety Action Program (3ERSAP) is studied here, not only with respect to when it started to work but also regarding

what would have happened if it had not been implemented. This is a novel assessment of the 3ERSAP, and helps to distinguish effects coming from European collaboration and within each country. Three methods are compared: synthetic control methods (SC), synthetic control with statistical learning (SCSL) and interactive counterfactual effects (ICE).

The overall view is that the implementation of the road safety program at European level had larger effects than if the countries had continued their own paths. This paper provides quantitative estimates for each country. At European level it is possible to say that the 3ERSAP in the year 2010 helped to avoid between 13,900 and 19,400 fatalities. This finding supports the idea that the 3ERSAP in particular, and the EU or international collaboration in general, provide results that were previously inaccessible for individual countries.

Regarding the different methodologies, an easy way to compare them is provided. In this particular case SCSL tends to perform better than SC and ICE.

JEL classification: C21, C22, K32, R41

Keywords: Road safety policy, European Union, synthetic control methods, policy evaluation, linear factor models

3.2 Introduction

"Over 1.2 million people die each year on the roads, with millions more sustaining serious injuries and living with long-term adverse health consequences. Globally, road traffic crashes are a leading cause of death among young people, and the main cause of death among those aged 15-29 years" according to the "Global Status on Road Safety" report by the World Health Organization in 2015. Furthermore, there are estimated effects of 1.8 % of the GDP in Italy, 0.6 % in Spain or 2.5 % in 2010 as reported by IRTAD (2012b) ¹. However, car accidents can potentially be avoided. Most of the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) countries are already trying to address

¹In Euros: 27.7 billion in Italy. 6.7 billion in Spain. 7.1 billion in Austria.

the problem in one way or another. Policies are very broad: from making some car equipment compulsory to changes in speed limits, education, road improvement, new road signs or advertisements among others. Some of which can be ongoing simultaneously, making assessments challenging² ³.

At a legal level the implementation of the different laws or agreements for road safety within the European Union (EU) can be cumbersome given the difficulties in combining all the different institutions implied in one way or another ⁴ In order to homogenize the transport in the EU the Transport White paper appeared in 2001, the reference for this document is EC (2001); with the initial target of halving the number of road victims by 2010. A target that will appear in the third European Road Safety Action Program (3ERSAP) from 2003 until 2010, which is the main objective of study here. In 2010 the target was not met in all countries but the overall road fatalities decreased by 43% between 2001 and 2010, see TRT et al. (2009), IRTAD (2010), IRTAD (2012a) and IRTAD (2013) for a study of the results and information for each country. However the assessment provide here distinguished between the 3ERSAP effects and each country effects. The questions this paper answers are: was the Third European Safety Action Program (3ERSAP) useful? And how big was its impact?, or is the fight against fatalities better off with a coordination at European level than at country level?

I try to answer those questions by introducing novel methodology that explic-

²It is a challenge for every single possible variable to disentangle the affect the behaviour and security of drivers have on the road. For an example of complexity for young novice drivers and how many different scenarios can be considered see Engström et al. (2003).

³Consider also the example of the advertisement and how not only the money spent on advertising could potentially affect driver's behaviours but the type of advertisement, see Castillo-Manzano and Castro-Nuño (2012) for a discussion.

⁴For example, to be able to drive in a different country with a valid license from another country may look simple, but from the moment it was granted until it becomes perfectly functioning is complex. Although it is possible to drive abroad it took some time until it became possible to punish foreign offenders, as can be seen in MEMO/11/483, from July 2011, in which the addressed the problem.

itly allows for short term comparison, namely synthetic control (SC) methods, synthetic control methods with Statistical Learning (SCSL) and Interactive Effects Counterfactual (ICE) as described in Abadie et al. (2010), Gobillon and Magnac (2015) and Valero (2017) ⁵. The techniques used here try to build, in their own way, counterfactual series making possible the comparison between real and observed data and what would have happened if the law (in this case: if the countries were continuing to carry out their policies at a country level without European level coordination and support) had not changed. The difference is the effect of the law, accounting for the rest of the effects as constants. I find that the methodologies can be useful for the questions posed. There is not one which is better than the other in absolute terms, therefore I recommend testing which is better in each case.

The closest research, I have found, with both similar methodology and within Europe are Campos et al. (2014) and Fernández and Garcia-Perea (2015). In Campos et al. (2014) there is quantification of the variation on GDP per capita for joining the European Union in comparison with their counterfactual equivalent in case those countries were not join. Authors showed a positive effect of around 12%. In Fernández and Garcia-Perea (2015) the inclusion within the Euro Area are studied, in this case the results indicate an overall slight improvement that disappeared through time. The methodology implemented in both is SC, I also include SCSL and ICE here.

Focusing on Europe and the road safety there are two works similar to this one. In Castillo-Manzano et al. (2014b) it is possible to find details about the road safety laws and implementation within the EU until 2009. Authors thought panel data estimation described a positive effect or *Europeanization*, this is: there is negative correlation between the number of years belonging to the EU and the traffic fatalities. There are evidences of the convergence of most

⁵I compare these three methodologies in a practical exercise later, but there are compelling ways to understand some of them as a sub-category of others. I will discuss more in Section 3.4.

of the countries of the EU, as described in Castillo-Manzano et al. (2014a). In this area of study this paper improves the literature by quantifying the effect due to the European intervention (3ERSAP).

The empirical results are that there is an overall positive effect of the 3ERSAP. Most of the countries had a decrease in the number of fatalities larger than what they would have had on their own. SCSL performed better most of the cases.

The structure of this paper is as follows, in Section 3.4 the methodology is explained, in Section 3.3 there more details about 3ERSAP, in Section 3.5 the results are described and in Section 3.6 the conclusions are drawn.

3.3 Third European Road Safety Action Program

3ERSAP spanned between 2003 and 2010. The background of the members were relatively different in general, as were their road safety policies. The free transport of products within the EU is a corner stone of the EU. In order to improve the transport at all level in 2001 the Transport White paper, EC (2001), was delivered. This document had an overall vision of the whole European transport system at the time. In this document appeared, for the first time what later became the 3ERSAP target: to half the number of road victims by 2010. This objective was ratified by the European Parliament and the Transport Council in 2003. In the same year, on the second of June, the European Commission presented the 3ERSAP, (CE, 2003), EUR-Lex - 52003DC0311. In this document the main areas of action and mechanism for evaluation and collaboration within the EU were well defined. It is possible that a country has their own particular objectives within their national plan, and to find a annual survey of most of the European countries within the annual IRTAD reports. Therefore there are records of most of the countries particular targets, policies and evolution.

3ERSAP had different measures and wanted to make it easier to measure

the results and easier to compare with other countries at all levels. The final evaluation of the program is officially TRT et al. (2009) which also helps to create the next (Forth) European Road Safety Action Program.

The 3ERSAP had 15 members in 2003 the beginning and finished with 27 in 2010⁶. From the beginning of 3ERSAP were: Belgium, France, Italy, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Germany, Denmark, Ireland, United Kingdom, Greece, Portugal, Spain, Austria, Finland and Sweden. On the first of May 2004 Hungary, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Slovakia and Slovenia joined. On the first of January 2007 Bulgaria and Romania did it too.

3.4 Methodology

Three methodologies are implemented: synthetic control (SC) methods, synthetic controls with statistical learning (SCSL) and interactive effects counterfactual (IEC).

SC was introduced by Abadie and Gardeazabal (2003) and developed in Abadie et al. (2010). In Valero (2017) the previous methodology is revisited in order to introduce Statistical Learning, the basic difference is how to choose the coefficients of the control units accounting for the bias-variance trade-off. Interactive Effects (IFE) is explained in Gobillon and Magnac (2015) among other techniques and here I follow one of their implementations: "Interative Effects: Counterfactual" (IEC)⁷, because of its simplicity and flexibility to detect effects through periods of time.⁸

Each methodology relies on different ideas: SC relies on the selection of

⁶Corresponding to the number of countries of the EU

⁷also known as Generalized Synthetic Control (GSC) Method in (Xu, 2015).

⁸For SC, software is provided by authors in R, Stata and Matlab, for SCEL it is generally implemented in many coding languages, the author focuses on Matlab. IEC is provided by the authors in R, I also provide a detailed description of the algorithm in the Appendix 3.7.2 as they describe it.

very similar units, therefore when one of them changes the others can still replicate the behavior of the changed one, see Abadie et al. (2010). SCSL use Statistical Learning techniques to select the units that are going to be used. The statistical learning techniques, in this particular case, are LASSO, at the cost of the determination of a complexity parameter, one way to do so is to use Cross-Validation⁹. IEC decomposes the series in factors, takes a number of them, r , according to their importance, to predict the objective series. Therefore IEC needs to select the complexity parameter r , which could be determined in different ways. For example Xu (2015) uses Cross-Validation and Bai and Ng (2002) analytical procedures but there is vast research in order to determine r , or similar parameters, in the literature. With these characteristics in mind it is reasonable to perform tests in each particular scenario to identify which could be the most suitable method. I do that by following Test 1 like in Valero (2017) but there are more possibilities within Statistical Learning.

For IEC it is very simple to introduce more than one treated unit (with caution given that r may be different). For SC and SCSL it is not as straight forward; one possibility is to apply the methodology to each country individually. However it is important to keep in mind that even if these cases are easy to implement in IEC, they may affect the results equally, if not account for them fully. As mentioned before, SCSL and IEC both require the specification of complexity parameters.

3.5 Results

Section 3.5.1 is a description of the data, implementation details are in Section 3.5.2 and the results with detail in Section 3.5.3.

⁹as explained in Valero (2017) and broadly implemented in software packages, such as Matlab, Stata, Python or R.

3.5.1 Data

The data comes from the International Road Traffic and Accident Database, IRTAD, from the OCDE. The variable used is fatalities per million inhabitants of each country¹⁰. There is annual data for Australia, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, Croatia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Korea, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Moldavia, Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, United Kingdom and United States, between 1970 and 2014. Here it is used from 1991 forward, given that in many cases, such as Germany. For an example see the data from Estonia in Figure 3.7, appears a pick within 1989 neighbourhood.

3.5.2 Implementation

I use the same countries and period of time for all the methods. The countries used as controls are: Australia, Canada, Croatia, Georgia, Iceland, Japan, Korea, Moldavia, New Zealand, Switzerland, Turkey, and United States. The number of latent factors, r , is chosen by using the lowest of different methodologies, a) Cross-Validation as in Xu (2015) and b) as in Bai and Ng (2002)¹¹. SC is applied here without a preintervention outcome, as in Valero (2017) with the so called Pseudo Synthetic Control method, to make it more comparable with the other methods, however still I will label it here as SC for the sake of simplicity. SCSL is implemented here via LASSO and Cross-Validation; to select the complexity parameter for LASSO I use Cross-Validation. I select as a starting point 2001, although the 3ERSAP was formally created in 2003, the reason is that countries started the negotiation even before 2001 and it could affect their policy.

¹⁰This variable summarizes summarized very well the success of the policies. It does not vary with migration, the construction of new road or droved kilometers as some countries use as a target making it very changing and dependent on unrelated factors.

¹¹although this is not particularly thought for this use.

3.5.3 Results

Selecting between SC, SCSL and ICE

Figure 3.1: Austria

One example is tracked here with detail; Austria. Austria's data is shown in Figure 3.1 (a). The rest of the countries' graphs are in "Appendix: Graphical Results". The graph also shows the real and counterfactual series depending on the methodology and when the change happened (the vertical line). By using a procedure I select a particular methodology, see "Appendix: Model selection" for details. For the case of Austria see Table 3.2.

The idea behind the test is that there are three different methodologies and it is necessary to select the one which yields the best results. To do that I consider the pre-treatment data and split it in 3 different random folds. From these 3 folds I use 2 to estimate (training and validation) the model and 1 to measure the effectiveness by calculating the MSE. I repeat the process many times and with the different methodologies. I select the one which provides better results

according to this procedure. The results of the evaluations are in Table 3.2 ¹².

Confidence Intervals

Once the best model is selected it is necessary to know if the difference between the counterfactual and the real series is significant. Figure 3.1 (b) depicts the selected approach with the interval of confidence at 95% probability. In the Austria example the real series lies outside the interval of confidence of the counterfactual, meaning that they are different with a 95% probability.

Effects

The results of all the countries with data are presented in Table 3.1. The first column shows the real effect; this is the difference between the number of fatalities per million inhabitants in 2000 and 2010. The name of the column is 'Real'. The second and third columns illustrate the effect due to the country alone according to the selected methodology. The name of the columns are 'Counterfactual Min' and 'Counterfactual Max'. 'Counterfactual Min' represents the lower bound of the confidence interval at 95% probability and 'Counterfactual Max' represents the upper bound of the confidence interval at 95% probability. In other words, 'Counterfactual Min' represents the minimum effect due to the country alone and 'Counterfactual Max' the maximum. The last two columns show the difference between the real and counterfactual columns. This shows us the effect not due to the country's normal patterns: the treatment effect; the effect of 3ERSAP. The idea is that if the effect cannot be totally explained by the counterfactual, then the remaining effect must have been caused by the 3ERSAP, given that the 3ERSAP is the largest factor that can affect them at a country level.

Continuing with Austria, the first column 'Real' of Table 3.1 in 2010 saw a reduction of 53 fatalities in comparison to 2001. The meaning of columns 'Counterfactual Min' and 'Counterfactual Max' is the number of fatalities which

¹²Also I provide the same table using the whole period of time available Table 3.3

Country	Real	Counterfactual	Counterfactual	3ERSAP Effect	3ERSAP Effect
		Min	Max	Max	Min
Austria	-53.1000	-16.5175	-37.6676	-36.5825	-15.4324
Belgium	-67.5000	-21.2371	-44.0819	-46.2629	-23.4181
Bulgaria	-28.4000	28.0629	4.5994	-56.4629	-32.9994
Denmark	-34.4000	-3.8710	-12.2144	-30.5290	-22.1856
Estonia	-84.1000	-242.3243	-332.5719	158.2243	248.4719
Finland	-32.8000	-3.2053	-5.0627	-29.5947	-27.7373
France	-71.6000	-29.2573	-30.7190	-42.3427	-40.8810
Germany	-40.1000	-15.3870	-23.2009	-24.7130	-16.8991
Greece	-58.9000	43.5884	23.3535	-102.4884	-82.2535
Hungary	-47.6000	-40.3154	-55.8506	-7.2846	8.2506
Ireland	-59.8000	22.2000	2.8000	-82.0000	-62.6000
Italy	-55.1000	-10.1630	-18.2271	-44.9370	-36.8729
Latvia	-117.3000	127.8000	-5.4000	-245.1000	-111.9000
Lithuania	-106.9000	36.3268	-32.0739	-143.2268	-74.8261
Luxembourg	-95.4000	-31.6016	-70.6803	-63.7984	-24.7197
Netherlands	-29.0000	0.5079	-5.8345	-29.5079	-23.1655
Norway	-18.4000	5.7628	-4.7852	-24.1628	-13.6148
Poland	-42.0000	43.1897	16.6033	-85.1897	-58.6033
Portugal	-72.7000	-9.2908	-39.2520	-63.4092	-33.4480
Romania	-16.7000	-12.9392	-22.7261	-3.7608	6.0261
Slovenia	-72.2000	-8.7681	-34.3872	-63.4319	-37.8128
Spain	-82.2000	-6.4756	-19.5170	-75.7244	-62.6830
Sweden	-37.1000	-1.8571	-14.3247	-35.2429	-22.7753
United Kingdom	-30.5000	-6.7164	-9.2677	-23.7836	-21.2323

Table 3.1: Effects decomposition. The units are fatalities per million inhabitants.

can be attributed to the country alone. If the expectation was a reduction between 16 ('Counterfactual Min') to 37 ('Counterfactual Max') fatalities, then there are between 15 and 36 fatalities due to an extraordinary circumstance that cannot be explained by the previous effort or behaviour of Austria. The last one will be the meaning of columns '3ERSAP Effect Max' and '3ERSAP Effect Min'. If we assume that there is no other source of changes than the 3ERSAP then this is a proxy for the 3ERSAP effect in each country. For Austria the 3ERSAP helped to save between 15 and 36 fatalities in 2010.

In the large majority of countries the effect was positive in 2010, apart from in Romania and Hungary. Following Table 3.1, multiplying the last two columns by the population of each country in 2010, it is possible to estimate the total number of fatalities avoided in the European Union in 2010 thanks to the 3ERSAP: between 13,900 and 19,400. In "Appendix: Graphical Results" I show the rest of the graphs with some comments for each country. This finding supports the idea that the 3ERSAP in particular, and the EU in general, provide results that were previously inaccessible for individual countries. This finding is in line with previous literature which studies the effects of belonging to different European multicountry level institutions, see Campos et al. (2014), Castillo-Manzano et al. (2014a) and Castillo-Manzano et al. (2014b).

Discussion about mechanisms

It is difficult to quantify exactly the mechanism that made the 3ERSAP successful overall. There are at least four factors that could have had a positive influence: A) the technology of the cars, given that it appeared as an aim of the project, and it makes sense given that the EU is a market with a population of around 500 million inhabitants. B) the creation of European institutions makes it easier to track, measure and compare the effect of the policies between countries. C) A better regulation of heavy transport could make the road more secure in general. D) The EU guidelines promote the participation of different stakeholders within each country. The study of each of the previous factors are

very interesting and the weight of each of them in the process remains unknown.

3.6 Conclusion

The coordination at European level fostered by 3ERSAP has yielded very positive results. The effect of 3ERSAP just in the year 2010 helped to save between 13,900 and 19,400 lives: lives that could not have been saved by the standard pre-3ERSAP mechanisms, i.e. countries' policies alone.

This finding also supports the idea that international collaboration helps to achieve goals which were previously out of reach of the countries on their own. In this particular case the European Union offers new possibilities otherwise unavailable for their members.

Regarding the different methodologies, an easy way to compare them is provided. In this particular case, SCSL tends to perform better than SC and ICE.

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3.7 Appendices

3.7.1 Appendix A: Model selection

In order to select a methodology or model there are ways to proceed, i.e. here I select between SC, SCSL and IEC. The idea behind model selection is that the original data can be split into three samples: training, validation and test. In the training sample I estimate the model, in the validation sample we can select hyperparameters and in the test sample I check the model, namely, I collect the Minimum Square Error (MSE). This procedure is repeated many times with different subsamples for training and validation and I select the procedure that is performing better. See Hastie et al. (2009) Chapter 7 for model selection. A possible procedure presented here is created following Valero (2017).

1. The pretreatment dataset is split in 10 random subsample.
2. One is reserved and not used for estimation. 9 subsamples are used for estimation.
3. The reserved data is used for assessing the previous estimate.
4. The results are gathered.
5. Previous steps are repeated 100 times.

Now the implementations are presented:

Table 3.3 and 3.2 show the quality of each technique for each country. It is worth noting that in both of them the best performer is SCSL. However, if we compare both tables in Table 3.2 the average MSE of PSCM and IEC are generally lower than in Table 3.3 but for SCSL it is higher. Although I should carry out further analysis, a preliminary explanation could be that because of the reduced amount of data PSCM and IEC tend to overfit, and SCSL is the only one able to not overfit. Furthermore, given that the values do not vary largely between 1991 and 2001, the prediction provided by SCSL could be very close to the real values.

Country	PSCM	SCSL	IEC
Austria	672.8516	49.9442	905.8705
Belgium	1016.7752	96.4328	1063.4076
Bulgaria	365.3885	24.9208	331.7244
Denmark	267.1754	81.4481	274.8566
Estonia	786.4097	74.5357	1527.3937
Finland	375.8887	9.5709	779.3942
France	496.0311	14.8141	516.6491
Germany	206.9307	16.0817	639.3450
Greece	452.5167	15.1635	384.9974
Hungary	25.8500	22.9947	90.4573
Ireland	432.8669	29.8386	829.9228
Italy	273.4653	37.7710	989.7348
Latvia	191.5752	23.7611	516.2557
Lithuania	356.0446	25.7626	643.8630
Luxembourg	179.9113	8.2983	122.6469
Netherlands	328.2812	85.2358	183.9618
Norway	668.0415	54.6026	1267.5781
Poland	20.8294	4.5822	149.1722
Portugal	435.9936	23.0702	476.1649
Romania	249.4321	30.4851	295.8966
Slovenia	722.8240	54.2572	3051.8251
Spain	120.4970	34.6778	583.1715
Sweden	522.3973	6.3388	475.9046
United Kingdom	628.7318	32.0475	942.9635

Table 3.2: Average MSE of Tests Results, from 1991.

Country	PSCM	SCSL	IEC
Austria	390.0937	111.1100	278.1585
Belgium	333.8025	132.2507	192.0267
Bulgaria	365.3885	111.1955	230.0088
Denmark	401.9245	81.4481	274.8566
Estonia	311.7073	134.4901	269.6181
Finland	395.1161	128.9533	268.9100
France	355.4734	148.5134	259.3455
Germany	358.9410	107.2037	261.1106
Greece	232.8575	130.8027	128.6379
Hungary	386.9384	96.7191	277.0625
Ireland	306.9154	122.9463	202.0129
Italy	183.8511	133.0463	158.1646
Latvia	258.8718	122.7386	234.6319
Lithuania	266.7859	92.7233	336.8504
Luxembourg	351.5627	166.3138	312.0127
Netherlands	328.2812	85.2358	183.9618
Norway	413.4671	119.0103	293.4153
Poland	316.7277	120.1840	180.9688
Portugal	293.8257	107.0625	295.0649
Romania	340.3578	126.4816	188.6755
Slovenia	310.6930	144.3393	235.1552
Spain	316.3529	119.5048	201.0235
Sweden	335.3099	147.2768	259.0514
United Kingdom	362.7593	130.5770	258.8786

Table 3.3: Average MSE of Tests Results, from 1970 .

3.7.2 Appendix B: Interactive Effects

Alternative methodologies exploit the panel data structure of the generic problem, which properties are well known, see (Pesaran, 2006) and (Bai, 2009). As a factor model:

$$y_{it} = \lambda_i' f_t + x_{it} \beta + \epsilon_{it} \quad (3.1)$$

with $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$ and $i = 1, \dots, N$. where x_{it} is a $p \times 1$ vector of observable regressors, β is a $p \times 1$ vector of unknowns coefficients, λ_i is $(r \times 1)$ is a vector of factor loading, and F_t is $(r \times 1)$.

- which dimension are $\frac{FF'}{T} = I$ and $\Lambda\Lambda'$ is diagonal.
- Note that: $\lambda_i' = (\hat{\lambda}_i, 1)'$ and $F_t = (1, \hat{F}_t)'$. Equivalent to have **Additive Effects**.
- Identification: $\frac{FF'}{T} = I$ and $\Lambda\Lambda'$ is diagonal.

Two Scenarios

Following the notation of Gobillon and Magnac (2015): there are at least two natural cases: a) IFE, treatment dummy and b) IEC counterfactual. IFE, treatment dummy will introduce a dummy for the treatment (i.e. $x_{it1} = 1$ if i is treated in period t , and $x_{it1} = 0$ if i is not treated in period t). However here I am interested in the evolution of the effect across time, therefore I do not use this approach. And b) it is carefully explained in the next subsection

Appendix: Interactive Effects Counterfactual Estimation

Here I provide a clear way to estimate Interactive Effects Counterfactual Algorithm:

- Step 1: Work with the untreated units. Obtain $\hat{\Lambda}^{Untreated}$, \hat{F} and $\hat{\beta}$.

$$Y^{Un} = \Lambda^{Tr} F + X^{Un} \beta + E_{it}$$

- Step 2: Work with the treated units in the pre-treatment periods. Obtain $\hat{\Lambda}^{Tr}$. *Until here*, GSC by (Xu, 2015).

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\Lambda}^{Treated} &= \underset{\check{\Lambda}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left(Y^{Tr} - \check{\Lambda}\hat{F} - X^{Tr}\hat{\beta} \right)' \left(Y^{Tr} - \check{\Lambda}\hat{F} - X^{Tr}\hat{\beta} \right) \\ &= \left(\hat{F}\hat{F}' \right)^{-1} \hat{F} \left(Y^{Un} - X^{Tr}\hat{\beta} \right)\end{aligned}$$

- Step 3: Create Counterfactual for treated units: \hat{Y}^{Tr} .
- Step 4: Re-estimate using the real data of untreated units and the counterfactual of treated units obtaining: $\hat{\Lambda}$, \hat{F} and $\hat{\beta}$, for a more efficient solution.

Asymptotic Properties

As pointed out in (Gobillon and Magnac, 2015), there are various asymptotic properties:

- If N and T tend to $+\infty$, then $\hat{\Lambda}^{Un}$, \hat{F} and $\hat{\beta}$, for the untreated are consistently estimated see (Bai, 2009).
- If additionally the T_0 tend to $+\infty$, then $\hat{\Lambda}^{Tr}$ is consistent.
- If N, T and T_0 tend to $+\infty$, then $\hat{\Lambda}$, \hat{F} and $\hat{\beta}$ are consistent.

3.7.3 Appendix C: Graphical Results

Here are the graphics the results for the countries with are having effects.

Austria

[H]

Figure 3.2: Austria

According to Figure 3.2 Austria benefited from 3ERSAP. According to IRTAD (2012a) Austria did not reach their target in 2010, i.e. 500 deaths was the target, Austria had 552. Their reference year was 2009. The key measures of the Austrian Road Safety Programme 2002-2010 were: the introduction of second-phase driver education; the demerit point system; alcohol screening; coaching for drunk drivers and seat belts campaigns.

Belgium

[H]

Figure 3.3: Belgium

According to Figure 3.3 Belgium benefited from 3ERSAP. According to IRTAD (2013) Belgium did not reach their target in 2010, i.e. 750 deaths, in the whole country, was the target, Belgium had 840. As shown in IRTAD (2010) some of the measures included a reduction of maximum speed limit for heavy load trucks, new breath tests and analyses, creation of a Road Safety Task Force among others.

Bulgaria

[H]

Figure 3.4: Bulgaria

Bulgaria joined the EU in 2007. According to Figure 3.4 Bulgaria benefited from 3ERSAP.

Denmark

[H]

Figure 3.5: Denmark

According to Figure 3.5 Denmark benefited from 3ERSAP. According to IRTAD (2010) Denmark set up their goal for 2012: 300 deaths in the whole country, however they had to alter it down to 200, given they reached it in 2007. Their main focus were young drivers, drink driving, bicycle safety and speeding.

Estonia

[H]

Figure 3.6: Estonia

Estonia does not appear to benefit from the 3ERSAP according to Figure 3.6. This is probably due to the strong reduction of fatalities per million inhabitants since 1999. If the years considered are extended we can appreciate that Estonia benefited, as depicted in Figure 3.7.

[H]

Figure 3.7: Estonia with data starting in 1970

Finland

[H]

Figure 3.8: Finland

According to Figure 3.8 Finland benefited. As it is possible to appreciate in Figure 3.8, from the year 1991 until 2001 the fatalities per million inhabitants was almost constant, and the 3ERSAP helped to break this tendency. Finland has their own very successful system, they set up their own target in shorter intervals (every four years) than most of the other 3ERSAP countries. They aimed for 250 deaths in 2010 in the whole country but unfortunately this was not reached, with 279 fatalities. They set this goal in 2006. Their target for 2025 is 100. For further detail see IRTAD (2010), IRTAD (2012a) and IRTAD (2013).

France

[H]

Figure 3.9: France

According to 3.9 the tendency of reduction of the fatalities was increased after the 3ERSAP. France has their own target, the closest one to this paper is 3000 fatalities in the whole country in 2012. It was established in 2007. They did not have a specific road safety programme. Their policy since 2007 has been oriented

towards having compulsory reflecting jacket and triangles in the car, as well as the reduction of alcohol intake when driving. the installation of interlock in the cars of driver has given positive BAC (blood alcohol concentration), mandatory for school buses and compulsory reflecting jacket and triangle. Particularly important were the implementation of graduated licensing system between 2007 and 2007 and the incrementation of seeped cameras in 2003. For further details see IRTAD (2010), IRTAD (2012a) and IRTAD (2013).

Germany

[H]

Figure 3.10: Germany

According to 3.10 the tendency of reduction of the fatalities was increased after the 3ERSAP. Germany did not have any explicit numerical target but is well recognised for their effort and their results have been named as one of the most important contributors for road safety in Europe, see IRTAD (2010). Particularly praised for their road network, their road policy vision of transport climate (e.g. aggressiveness) and technological importance.

Greece

[H]

Figure 3.11: Greece

It is possible to validate 3.11 by comparing with a longer period of time as in Figure 3.12. Therefore the 3ERSAP helped to reduce the fatalities, however it is necessary to point out that Greece started a few years earlier to modernize their road security plan, therefore the effect of 3ERSAP could be combined. Greece had two road safety strategic plans in the considered period. a) Between 2001-2005: with the aim of reduction of a 20% the fatalities. It was almost achieved: 19%. b) Between 2006-2010, it aimed to achieve the 50% European target however they achieve a reduction of 37% at a national level. During this period of time were implemented the first basic measures in Greece in order to face the road safety issue. Still there is a lag of policies to be implemented, such as lack of coordination and monitoring, see IRTAD (2010) and IRTAD (2013).

[H]

Figure 3.12: Greece with break in 2001, starting in 1970

Hungary

[H]

Figure 3.13: Hungary

According to Figure 3.13 Hungary did not benefited from 3ERSAP in 2010. In 2002 in terms of fatalities, Hungary established a reduction of 30% by 2010 and 50% by 2015, taking as a reference 2001. The main policies were child seat obligation (2002), stricter demerit point system (2008) and higher technical requirements for child restraints (2009). Hungary reached its goal for 2010 and almost the equivalent for the proposal in 3ERSAP.

Ireland

[H]

Figure 3.14: Ireland

According to Figure 3.14 Ireland benefited from 3ERSAP. Ireland had a Road Safety Strategy 2007-2012. In terms of fatalities the main target was to reduce to 60 fatalities per million inhabitant by 2012. They reached it in 2010. Between 2000 and 2010 they reach almost a 50% reduction of fatalities. Their policy went from education in schools, enforcement, engineering and evaluation of their initiatives, see IRTAD (2012a).

Italy

[H]

Figure 3.15: Italy

According to Figure 3.15 Italy benefited from 3ERSAP. Italy almost reached its 50% reduction target. Italy invested more than 920 million Euros and implemented more than 1600 local projects, as can be seen in IRTAD (2013).

Latvia

[H]

Figure 3.16: Latvia

According to Figure 3.16 Latvia benefited from 3ERSAP. Latvia reached the 50% reduction target.

Lithuania

[H]

Figure 3.17: Lithuania

According to IRTAD (2012a), Lithuania reached their goal, in line with 3ERSAP.

Luxembourg

[H]

Figure 3.18: Luxembourg

According to Figure 3.18 Luxembourg benefited from 3ERSAP. Luxembourg did not reach the 50% reduction target, but shaved a decrease of around 34%.

Netherlands

[H]

Figure 3.19: Netherlands

According to Figure 3.19 Netherlands benefited from 3ERSAP. The Netherlands did not follow the generic target of a 50% reduction. They had their own target for 2010 of 750 traffic fatalities. The target was reached by 2007. In 2008 they placed a new target of 500 for 2020, for further details see IRTAD (2010).

Norway

[H]

Figure 3.20: Norway

According to Figure 3.20 Norway benefited from 3ERSAP. Norway did not have a particular target in terms of fatalities. They adopted a "Vision Zero" goal in their National Plan of Action for Traffic Safety 2002-2011. The "Vision Zero" involves the entire transport policy, however they made their priority the reduction of head-on crashes and collisions with pedestrians. They established a new goal for 2020, equivalent to the 33% with 2010 as a base year, i.e. 775. for more details see IRTAD (2012a).

Poland

[H]

Figure 3.21: Poland

According to Figure 3.21 Poland benefited from 3ERSAP. Poland has a National Road Safety Program for 2005-2017, called GARMBIT 2005. It is a "Vision Zero" plan with the particular target of a reduction of 50% fatalities in 2013 with respect to 2003, i.e. 2800. See IRTAD (2012a) for further details. This target was not reached as shown in ITF (2015).

Portugal

[H]

Figure 3.22: Portugal

According to Figure 3.22 Portugal benefited from 3ERSAP. Portugal also has similar but not exactly the same goals as in 3ERSAP, for more detail of Portugal goal see IRTAD (2010). In particular taking as base year 1998-2000 they had 1748 fatalities and they wanted to reduce them by 50%. In 2008 they reached their target with 776 (-55%).

Romania

[H]

Figure 3.23: Romania

Romania joined the EU in 2007. In Figures 3.23 and 3.23 it is possible to see results from 2001 and 2007. There is no evidence that in 2001 the 3ERSAP had started affecting Romania.

[H]

(a) Comparison

(b) With Interval of Confidence

Figure 3.24: Romania

Slovenia

[H]

(a) Comparison

(b) With Interval of Confidence

Figure 3.25: Slovenia

According to Figure 3.25 Slovenia benefited from 3ERSAP. Slovenia's target was 124 fatalities and the goal was almost reached.

Spain

[H]

Figure 3.26: Spain

According to Figure 3.26 Spain benefited from 3ERSAP. Spain reached their target reduction in line with the 3ERSAP and even better reaching a reduction of 55% in 2010. For further details see IRTAD (2010), IRTAD (2012a) and IRTAD (2013).

Sweden

[H]

Figure 3.27: Sweden

According to Figure 3.27 Sweden benefited from 3ERSAP. Sweden has a "Vision Zero" policy and a very developed system that made them have one of the lowest ratios fatalities per million of inhabitants. For further details of their systems in particular cases that occurred in the considered periods see IRTAD (2010), IRTAD (2012a) and IRTAD (2013).

United Kingdom

[H]

Figure 3.28: United Kingdom

According to Figure 3.28 United Kingdom benefited from 3ERSAP. United Kingdom has its own program and target. In particular their target for 2010 was a reduction of 40% with respect to 1997-98. They reached their target with a reduction of 49%. For further details see IRTAD (2010), IRTAD (2012a) and IRTAD (2013).

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